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Leading New Generation Knowledge while Reforming the Teaching Process A Study Case in Albanian Universities

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ABSTRACT

In our paper we will have an overview and a case study in Albanian Universities about the new generation of leading knowledge from university to their life. How teaching leadership role and managing -practicing methods need to be applied and how much they have improved students life and which is the real impact! Such Research questions that awaken interest in this field of study (Leading Education) are the objectives of this research (paper). After the 90's, Albania experienced a series of dramatic changes in the economic, political and social aspects. Inevitably, Higher Education became part of this transitional phase, which continues to exist in Albania. The development of higher education faces every day with new challenges, such as infrastructure development, financial and institutional autonomy management, integration into the European education system, etc. All of these have affected the profound and frequent transformations of the entire higher education system, its education, its policies and resources, which, by the way they are managed, leave an impact on individual and social life by defining so, the true nature of the system. Some of these problems are placed in the center of attention in our paper, in order to show that In every aspect of learning, should be found the embryos of a vital experience, of a problems posed, from the giving of new knowledge to the organization, the direction and leading of the independent work of students by the pedagogues-(as a leader), giving priority to individual and collective creativity in function of development.

Keywords: *Leading, Knowledge generation, Policies and Resources, Priorities, Impact in life*

Introduction

The preparation of human products from the university requires a new philosophy of learning, which means; combining traditional learning with analytical one, critical and creative learning, where the main purpose is to develop knowledge independently from the students themselves.

The university should provide student self-knowledge, which is the basis of their intellectual development. Even in the cases of high level of pedagogical knowledge, it can not fully achieve its goals if it is students do not create intellectual expressive habits, in order to work every day, and not simply to reproduce, but to process information creatively, to analyze-verify and implement it.

In fact School remains the foundation of knowledge and culture, which will and should cultivate intellectual skills and abilities for critical and analytical learning (1) Unfortunately, not only learning, but also passive thinking, reproductive and mechanical thinking, it is cultivated in kindergarten or childhood, and also in university, and consequently follows a profession as a specialist of every field: teacher-leader, economist, doctor, lawyer, politician etc.

Practice and life can teach a lot to people. They can stimulate and fasten the critical thinking, but the efficiency, is too small (especially with students where the opportunities are greater) To learn not only in order to acquire a wealth of knowledge being successful in the exam, but above all, to be able to transform the acquired knowledge into a useful product. Such a kind of learning is called "learning by doing".

It is a mistake to think that these problems are not related to the work of the lecturer and the university and school in general. The connection is straightforward. On one hand the school has been and remains the teaching and cultural institution that gives solid, organized and systematic knowledge. On the other hand, it is the school that has had and has more conservatism. It has been quite formalized and has also had frozen pedagogical structure!

Literature Review and Hypothesis

Along the view that we are extending here, the basic imperfection that is still imperceptible is always passive learning, mechanical learning and reproductive one. Memory, even the mechanical one, is worth in every kind of job, much more in learning. You need also to learn by heart. But these are just the beginning of the mental activity, while the prevalence of reproductive learning limits this activity to the primitive and infantile stage. It solidifies and standardizes thinking, nourishes scholarship, dogmatism, and even conformism. It does not allow any space to self-conscious attitude, to persuasive convenience through proofs, confrontation, and discussions and controversy that is required for the recognition of truth. And what is the worst? Is that the students carry the fruits of this learning for a long time in life and work. Too much later, really later, the student can begin to work on his own mind.

Without denying the achievements and efforts made in this regard, mechanical learning remains a negative phenomenon that hinders the achievement of the required quality level.

University teaching experience, shows that the student's enjoyment of these skills is at a slower extent. In this regard, it obstructs the opinion as students read freely, the more they learn the lessons and the more they improve their skills to analyze and encapsulate the school material. This seems unrealistic. Proofs for this are the written exams where reproduction prevails.

It is still present that the fulfillment of student formation is extended enough to achieving the good results during the exam and the comfort of knowledge that students are able to derive during

the formal exam. The reflexion, perception and experience of students on scientific knowledge are often ignored. In addition, in front of the logical questions, most students are not able to defend or reject a statement at a time when they remember many theories and formulas, so they can not distinguish what is essential, as they reproduce entire pages of the book.

It is not enough to stay attached to the problem, but to make a face-to-face and radical confrontation, escalated over time, of the old conception and practices combined with searching for new ways, forms and methods, embodied to the problems that require solutions(2).

In the last two decades, multiple research has shown that students develop thinking skills more effectively if they are currently involved with the materials they are studying. These research has led to the discovery and development of a number of theories and new strategies on active learning. But these researches and developments are valid when are presently applied. It is paradoxical that higher education, through theory and scientific research in the field of education has provided many innovations for education at all levels of education, and has often failed to implement these innovations. Still in nowadays the method where pedagogues speak and students listen dominate at the universities auditorium. It is important not only to recognize the nature and strategies of active learning, but also the usual barriers and barriers that increase the resistance of pedagogues to realistically implement these strategies.

H-1. *Teachers as a leader must encourage an active, continuing communication of concerns, observations, data, insights and suggestions, from and among students themselves.*

H-2. *The key question is how many fresh, innovative, shared, implementable ideas would be successful?*

What will make things different in 21-st century is that the world is going through a transformation that effects industrial world as well as social, political and economic one. The world is being fundamentally reshaped by the information and technology. (*Collin Powell "The leadership secrets of Collin Powell" pp 37 -38, published in USA 2002 by Oren Harari and R.R.Donnely*).

Traditional learning is the reproduction of knowledge. Here the student is seen to be fulfilled with knowledge. But knowledge is not static and students should not be seen as passive part in acquiring knowledge but as an active part of creating their knowledge. They must actively participate in the learning process. (3)

Figure 1: Traditional teaching and reproduction of knowledge

Students should write, discuss, and engage in problem solving, they should be evolve in the implementation of an action plan. The pedagogue as a Leader has the purpose of structuring, orienting, guiding and analyzing ideas. The student assisted by a pedagogue as a Leader is consistently involved in tasks to a high level of thinking; to analyze, to synthesize, to evaluate by creating their own beliefs on what they think. The interconnected learning contexts support the building of knowledge. When students work in groups and do activities, in order to increase reflective thinking about what they are doing; then he/she (students themselves) will to be able to use the knowledge gained in resolving problem situations in life and society.

It is important to consider what the student is having on his head without seeing as a duty filling their head. The pedagogue as a leader will thus guide the modeling and intellectual formation of the most responsive students for the accomplishment of their duties. This requires that pedagogue as a leader should have the minimum of triple training personally, scientifically, methodologically and didactically.

About the Philosophy of Professional Training in Albanian Universities

1) Market economy requires people capable of having clear concepts of contemporary science and technology, as well as intellectual habits and necessities for the trade-market, which has a great deal of flexibility. New models of business and new business practices are being developed. Consequently, new types of new and diverse employees will be required to work in jobs that has never existed. This new job order is focusing heavily on knowledge, on learning and on innovation, consequently these terms are getting a new meaning.

Now knowledge is not encyclopaedic knowledge, but innovation. Innovation is quality and quality control is knowledge management. Knowledge society is fueling the change of opportunity for education, school, and university of the 21st century. We need to change the mental patterns that give life to the metamorphosis of education. All teachers, students, parents, and those who make the necessary decisions need to think differently.

2) The great scientific flux in the century adds the demand for knowledge for the next two or three decades. This is because during manufacturing activity, within the same generation, the work character changes and while science has become a productive force, then every man should complete their knowledge, not only once. It is estimated that during 1999-2002 the amount of new information produced globally is approximately equal to the amount of information produced throughout history. As a result, education and efficient learning can not be focused only on the transmission of information portions that are often memorized and form a ‘frozen Knowledge Magazine’ says Karen Sewell of New Zealand University and you can easily understand that’s why the XXIst century education should redimension!

3) It is not the amount of knowledge that determines the preparation of new specialists, but the skills and how to make this skills efficient to work independently.

In forming such a personality, our school plays an important role, from which today it is required to equip students with the methodology of learning and working, promoting the *art of initiative* and the *independence of thought* and action.

From this, it follows the basic task for all school categories, but especially for the University "not to fill up the student's head, but to build right their own head"

This means that "universities must produce qualitative minds (brain) and not just heads filled with knowledge, giving so priority to individual creativity and collective ones, for sake of development".

The Advantages and Disadvantages of Public Education in Albanian Universities

The Albanian Universities in long term have experienced a lot of crises and changes in Law of the Higher Education from the parliament, but still they offer stability in society as the followings:

- ❖ Albanian Universities have a longer history in teaching. They are safe and lifelong.
- ❖ They have an extension throughout the country and satisfy the needs of the overwhelming majority of the population.
- ❖ No intention for profit, as a private universities, but they raise up the academic level and promote the elite’s creation
- ❖ Trade market has verified the quality of teaching in public universities.
- ❖ They are inexpensive and can have access to all stratas of population.
- ❖ In addition to teaching, there also offer scientific research, one of the main criteria university integration.
- ❖ Qualified and Permanent Staff

In this clear and synthetic way, it is shown that the production of quality human products from the university requires a new philosophy of learning, that is to say, not the acquisition of knowledge, but the acquisition of intellectual skills to search for, to solve, to control, in order to apply through the diversity of arguments, trials and justifications.

Teacher or pedagogue as a Leader should guide students towards this path. Then they are free to choose themselves.

"If a person possesses such skills will surely be able to adapt to the progress and change compared to another person whose preparation is basically oriented towards the accumulation of knowledge rather than the logical processing of knowledge "emphasizes Ainstain.

KNOWLEDGE says Professor M. Castell (ranked in 2006 in fifth place as the author quoted by the Social Science Quotation Index) – it is not the thought on "s.m.th", something produced by human thought and subsequently codified then into disciplines by special experts. Precisely, knowledge today is understood as something like energy, something determined by its effect on action, from the results that are achieved. Knowledge is not something that can be determined or measured, but it is a generating force, a dynamic power or the capacity to do things.

So, knowledge today is defined and appreciated, not for what it is, but for what it can be done. The new meaning is distinctly seperated from the traditional meanings of knowledge, as the eternal truth that is readily available from the book or the teacher.

So we will have to renew the goals of education and the methods by which these goals are achieved, because schools in the 21st century will produce and will not consume knowledge. They will develop new sources of communication. Such sources, unlike from print texts allow you give knowledge by new tools such as images, sounds, gestures (blogs, video interviews, live recordings, etc).

The effort to help the student build a set of functional groups is a clear sign of the great relocation from encyclopedic knowledge to the new culture of active-thinking. If we want to prepare a new generation, in order to be adapted with thought, we should focus not on knowledge, but on the skills-what can they do with their knowledge?

Constructive Theory of Education Leading

According to the theory of Piaget's constructivism, man is seen as an active subject in constructing his own knowledge and learning. Education is seen as being compatible with existing knowledge of the subject and information coming from the natural and social environment. (4)

This theory describes the process of learning. It is related to pedagogical techniques that encourage learning or active learning. Scientific constructivism is seen as a scientific method for the philosophy of learning in which students actively build their knowledge. Learning should be active in fuction of constructing and developing knowledge and skills. But we often fall victim to the belief that what we explain to students is what they learn.

We need to focus more on what the students learn than just what we explain. Active engagement is the essence of the constructive method, because students can build their knowledge critically and analytically, better than getting ready by the pedagogue. The process of learning should be

conceived as a sketched building, constructed and enriched by students themselves. This building contains interweaving, listening, writing, observing, thinking, acting. The quintessence of this building depends on the equilibrium of these elements.

Everyone has his own learning habits or appropriate styles that help him/her utilize his/her ability to accomplish the goal that they have. Each person can dominate one of the styles more than others, or can use Different styles in several circumstances. If classroom activities only include a particular style of learning, as is the case of the traditional lectures where students mostly listen, the results are achieved from those students who have this dominant learning style.

Others find themselves at the lowest level of the class and this certainly creates and strengthens the opinion that some are awake and some others are unable to recognize different learning styles and including different activities in accordance to characteristics, skills, and student experience individually or as a group. This will increase the quality of learning for all students. But learning styles do not have the effect on student achievement in different active learning environments. (5) There are many active learning techniques and all of them, regardless of learning styles, they work. Students learn better when they are actively involved in this process. Studies have shown that we remember 20% of what we hear, 50% of what we see and 80% of what we do. We learn from experience, we learn in interaction with others, and with everything that surrounds us and we do it all the time since we were born. Without this combination, we would get less. (6)

In order for knowledge to be functional, students should know how and where to use this knowledge. Lessons can be theoretical or practical, whether they involve thinking or acting. It is not enough just to learn new concepts and their theoretical development.

Theoretical learning can be tested in new situations and may not be effective. Also, it is not enough, just the experience of learning. Without reflecting on this experience, it can be forgotten. Lessons should be combined with thinking and acting, while students should be able to make the connection between theory and practice. It is not enough to act, as it is not enough just to think. Thinking through experience realizes connectivity through thinking and acting. (7)

Figure 2

According to David Kolb, learning is seen as a combination of learning from a concrete experiences, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization and active experimentation, which

follow each other according to a closed cycle shown in fig 2. In this cycle it can be started at any point, but the next steps follow the cycle again.

Constructing functional and coherent scientific models occurs spontaneously for most students. They must perform various activities that help to build functional models. Making to work the mechanism of this cycle, it involves students inevitably in the activities of thinking and acting. The learning process and cycles are continually evolving and affecting people throughout life that is reflected in relationships between theory and practice. We learn ideally when we realize each element of the learning cycle. Any failure in solving a task would come as a result of the failure in realizing the steps of the learning cycle.

A) Concrete Experience

Students are involved in an active exploration of experience such as ideas and assumptions, based on concrete ideas. It is a step where the student becomes aware of the use of knowledge in practice. Collected experience creates certainty for students. For example, a lecture can begin with everyday life applications, which involves students in the safest way, as every student has in their daily experience, similar examples.

B) Reflective Observations

Students are involved in discussions where they reflect on their experiences critically, without accepting as sufficient their solely personal experience. Here the student begins to reveal his self-reliance, since he is the one who, after bringing his experience, reflects on himself over this experience. This is a step where constructive debat can be encouraged, where students themselves consciously admit what is wrong or right.

C) Abstract Conceptualization

Learning from the experience is not just exploration of experience and reflection on it. Students should be able to structure their ideas on concepts and theories and logically move in an action plan to create models and develop the theory. This step realizes the connection between winning experience, individual ideas and their harmonization with ideas, concepts and models of others. This is the discussion of conceptual thoughts and abstract ideas, an important element that can be included in every part of the lesson that enables inclusion in the recognition, confrontation, and analysis of ideas and views in function of the teaching process. This is a step in the development, about the consolidation and further improvement of students as a part of modern society.

D) Active Experimentation

Accountable students implement the action plan by testing their ideas and concepts, practicing patterns through experimentation by gaining their skills in the future. Students are enabled to make decision-making processes, logical and acceptable after judgment, analysis and dealing with outcome.

The role of the pedagogue in an active and leadership teaching environment. A leader should help to create learning opportunities and enable others to recognize and use these opportunities. The leader should provide assistance during each element of the learning cycle, through the creation of a suitable environment for learning, providing an activity that will begin the learning process, creating a favorable atmosphere for constructive critical examination of knowledge.

Aims of the Active Learning Method

Active learning methods that integrate thinking into action have two important goals: make the class more dynamic by turning it into an environment where the student is not just a figure, but also a voice creating the students intellectual skills, in order to work every day, and not just to reproduce, but to process creative information in a creative way to encapsulate and implement it. In order for students to succeed, they should increase their confidence in their ability to learn and to process all the scientific information In and Out of the Class. Duties and their continuous assessment will force students to take their role by not staying passive.

"If the student - said Ainstain – has exercised his muscles and physical fitness through gymnastics and activities, he would later be able to perform any physical work. This is also applied to the development of mental abilities and the skillfulness of his hands – concludes Ainstain.

"If you want to shape and strengthen the mind of the student," Ruso says, give them a chance to work, to be ready to act, to be constantly moving. And this is achieved by realizing from them an effort to write a report, essay or a simple memorization, an interpretation, a translation of a text or article, resolving an equation and practicing a sport.

So, according to C.Powell to be successful, leaders must consciously work to stay in touch with the best ideas of the people that you lead, in our case the students.

So, in order to answer the **H-2(hypothesis 2)**.The key question is how many fresh, innovative, shared, implementable ideas would be successful? The answer is that:

It is not only the process to harvest ideas, but it is also the process of involving people in and making them taking responsibility for shaping of their ideas.

A good leader may unleash a flood of interesting and provocative insight, but the ultimate goal is to inspire students not just to *voice* the problem, but also to *figure out* ways to solve problems.

Results and Aims of Pedagogue Rreflection Standards as a Leader

The teaching and teaching standards describe what distinguishes a professional from a non-professional. In this way, the knowledge, skills and values needed for teaching are highlighted.

Standards reflect the beliefs and values of the persons involved in the drafting process. In this way, they point out the need to ensure that approved training programs prepare members of the vocational profession, capable, and able to Form students as citizens of the future;

All these effort and action are taken into consideration in order to:

- To emphasize the responsibility of the teacher's profession in improving students' learning.
- To set a point because being a teacher means having a unique professional experience that does not have other professions

- To clarify knowledge, competences and inseparable values from teaching
- To establish the basics of a continuous professional and personal development.
- To present the aspirations and aims of the teacher's/pedagogue (Leader) as a profession
- To give the right values to the dignity of the teacher's/pedagogue (Leader) profession
- To recognize and accept teacher's/pedagogue (Leader) contributions in Albania
- To support teacher's/pedagogue (Leader) and organizations in improving eaching processs, for the public interest.

Of course during such processes and effort of changes and improvement for further development in Higher Education in University may occur any failure or any handicap?

The answer is Don't punish for failure ; As long as you are not subjecting your organization to undue risk,its never *sin to fail* when pursuing a good objective using sensible-effective tools and tactics .Find ways not to make the same mistake twice.

1-Challenge the pros to get better solutions. Whether the situations is challenging you or your subordinate students is challenging you, remember that more opinion and more voices translates into more alternative opinion. This is particularly important when events are moving faster than your collective experience has prepared you for.

2-Emphasize, dignity, respect, and honor while disagreeing!

3-Be patient!

If you are right the wheel will eventually turn into your way

4- Built a setting in which all feel free to speak out

If you are going to be speaking out, you need to be helping others to speak out, too. (It's the best way to get ideas on the table) Encourage those around you to challenge you and the other students or members of the team. Through standards it is acknowledged that the professional teacher/pedagogue as a leader uses different styles and methods for effective teaching. Standards are based on: professional and personal growth, which is done continuously and that a teacher/pedagogue as a leader passes through different stages during his career as:

- interpersonal
- Pedagogical
- Scientific Skills
- Organizational Aspects

According to Weber, there can be no successful policies without the principle of honesty, and this remarkable man throws the message that without seeking the impossible, we can not achieve the impossible; *nothing is impossible*

Methodology

The methodology used is that of observation and testing students by the projects that we as a pedagogue-leader have planned with the groups of students in University of Vlora, specifically students of Natural sciences .Multiple researches has shown that students develop thinking skills

more effectively if they are currently involved with the materials they are studying! The projects were implemented in order to test knowledge taken and students' creativity and critical thinking.

Conclusions

First, the higher education system still does not sufficiently respond to the needs of the future of society and the economy of the country.

Many aspects of Higher Education, in particular the level of teaching and research in higher education institutions (HEI-s), have not responded to the dynamics of changes in Albanian society and its inclinations!

If we want to prepare the new generation to adapt to the change, we must focus not only on knowledge, but on the skills-what we can do with our knowledge? .

We stick to the idea that our universities do not form students with the right sense and skills to apply their knowledge flexibly in practice. The factors influencing are not only individual experience, talents, competitive abilities, culture, social values associated with the student, but also they related to the school itself. The key factor is that academic-curricula should provide the opportunity to practice the knowledge taken at school in order to enrich students' experiences.

Another important factor is the new viewpoint of the triangle *knowledge-student-pedagogue* where the pedagogue leads students and students construct and develop knowledge by acting and doing .This not only in school but throughout life. The design of new figures to the student is made through the application of high intellectual abilities to achieve interpretation, analyzing, synthesizing and evaluating learning.

Another important factor is the new philosophy of learning as a process that generates sustainable knowledge, values, emotions, feedback, creativity, self-action, leadership and management skills.

Information technology provides opportunities for rapid and radical change. There are many ways to reform the teaching process, but all require changing the concepts of learning by integrating thinking and acting, planning a clear and flexible program, implementing strategies and methods in line with the conditions and resources we have, the awareness of the students with the trade market in accordance with the personal and social perspective. In this way, to all students interested and motivated University offers them very good opportunities for a more productive career.

Such inclination are in perspective with the Future progress to be achieved!

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